

Hierarchical of Needs Driving Thai Teenagers to Consuming Facial Cream

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Abstract— Currently, Thai teenagers tend to use more facial cream for different reasons. Therefore, there is a need to choose a multi-level facial cream, ranging from basic needs to self-actualization needs to reach their true potential that is physiological needs and self-actualization needs, respectively. This study was applied Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory to convey various levels of needs that play crucial parts in decision to choose facial cream among Thai teenagers. Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory presents the five levels of needs that drives motivation, consisting of physiological needs, safety needs, belongingness and love needs, self-esteem needs and self-actualization needs. Based on a survey with 80 Thai teenagers aged 10-19 years who choose to use facial cream, the result shows arranged in descending order of mean scores as follows, physiological needs, self-actualization needs, safety needs, self-esteem needs and belongingness and love needs by 4.46, 4.41, 4.10, 3.96, 3.69, respectively. All of these have a full score of 5 points. The correlation test revealed that all five needs levels were all positive and there were only very low to moderate correlations. This shows the relationship between Thai teenagers' preferences in choosing facial creams.

Keywords— Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, Needs, Facial cream, Teenagers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, facial creams are widely used among teenagers who love facial care and want to have a better skin in many countries. Especially Thailand, which is a country with a tropical climate and has a very high pollution problem. As a result, the facial skin is often affected from dust. Therefore, Thai teenagers tend to use more facial cream for different reasons ranging from, physiological needs to the need that make themselves satisfied with the highest efficiency of using facial cream. Abraham Harold Maslow is a professor of psychology at the Brandeis University. He has developed the hierarchy theory needs came up to explain human needs. Maslow believes that human behavior can be explained by a person's tendency to find goals that will satisfy their life desire and gain something meaningful to oneself. It is true to say that the process of motivation is at the heart of Maslow's theory of personality, As he believes that humans are demanding animals and it is difficult for humans to reach the stage of complete satisfaction. In Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, when a person desires to be satisfied and when a person is satisfied with something, they continue to demand satisfaction for another. Which is the trait of a human being who always wants to get things. Maslow ranks human needs from the beginning to the next step in order as follows,

1. Physiological needs

It is the most powerful basic need and most noticeable. The satisfaction obtained at this stage will stimulate need at a higher level and if a person fails to satisfy this basic need, it will not be motivated to a higher level of need. However, if a need isn't satisfied a person will be subject to that need forever. Which makes other need did not appear or became a secondary requirement. Therefore, teenagers have basic needs to use facial cream from the physical appearance of their original skin because of the feeling of wanting to care,

maintain and restore the health of the skin on the face to be better.

2. Safety needs

When the physical needs are satisfied, the person continue to develop to a next level. This stage is called the need for safety or a sense of security. The skin is a constantly changing organ. Each month, our skin has shed old skin cells when our skin is exposed to pollution. It will cause free radicals in the skin dust, smoke, dirt, stains can clog pores and cause acne. Teenagers tend to use facial cream to protect their skin from UV light, pollution and dust.

3. Belongingness and Love needs

This need arises when the physical need and safety need received a response. A person wants to gain love and belonging by building relationships with others such as relationships within the family or with others members within a group will be an important goal for a person. Many teenagers choose to use facial cream because they want to restore their skin to be beautiful, smooth without acne and wrinkles until the close people became interested and adore their face, even some teenagers choose to use facial creams to attract the people they secretly love or admire to focus on and love them.

4. Self-Esteem needs

When the need for love and affection to others is reasonable and makes a person satisfied. The thrust of the third stage will be reduced and the need on the next step to replace. That is to say, human beings want to be respected in two ways namely, (4.1) self respect is the need for power have confidence in yourself, be strong and capable in yourself. Many teenagers are afraid to reveal their face to others. So, choose to use the app to customize your own face to look beautiful but this solution is to solve the problem with the root cause, not the consequence. We should choosing a solution

that gives long-term results is to use a facial cream to enhance your personality and regain your self confidence. (4.2) esteem from others is the need for dignity, to be praised, accepted, get attention, has reputable and get rejoice. Sometimes, being recognized for our own beauty from the eyes of others makes us appreciate ourselves and see the advantages of own self. In contrast, this lack of acceptance leads to feeling and attitudes of inferiority, feeling of inadequacy and feeling weakness

5. *Self-Actualization needs*

To the final hierarchy, if the prior hierarchy need has effectively caused satisfaction, the need to truly understand own self will arise. Maslow explain the need to truly understand own self, it is the desire for everything that a person is able to obtain appropriately. A person who achieves this ultimate level will use their full power in challenging tasks and their potential and a desire to improve own self. Most though not all, humans being seek to achieve perfection within themselves, the ultimate goal of teenagers choosing facial cream is to have perfect skin but that takes a longer time than our skin to be beautiful and bright white skin as expected. Some people, may give up their efforts along the way or some people look forward to fighting and not backing down. Finally, what is the need to truly understand own self?, that is what we need to find within ourselves and draw it out to best match our abilities.

This research aimed to investigate motivation in different hierarchy of needs according to the Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory that drives Thai teenagers to choose to use facial cream ranging from the physiological needs to the needs that make themselves satisfied with the maximum efficiency of the use of facial cream and find out at what stage of needs affects to choose to use of facial cream of Thai teenagers the most.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study was a cross-sectional analytical study. Using a questionnaire consisting of 5 questions showing the motivation to use facial creams of Thai teenagers according to the Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory namely, Physiological needs, Safety needs, Belongingness and Love needs, Self-Esteem needs, Self-Actualization needs. The researcher developed it as a tool for data collection. An online survey was randomly distributed to Thai teenagers aged 10-19 years in the central region who regularly to use facial cream and a total of 80 people responded to the online survey. After that, the data was analyzed using descriptive statistics namely, frequency distribution and percentage. In the case of continuous data, the mean must be analyzed and standard deviation. Including, use inferential statistics namely, estimation and hypothesis testing. Shows the motivation of Thai teenagers towards all 5 levels of needs and shows average scores based on 5-Likert scaling responses, it is a measure used to allow commenters in closed-ended questionnaires to have options ranging from, strong disagreement to strong agreement. Then, the data obtained from the analysis were put in the frequency distribution table to choose the description that best conveys their actual

motivation. Finally, a correlation test was performed to reveal how these types of motivation are related statistically.

III. RESULT

According to table 1, Thai teenagers aged 10-19 years respondents tended to strongly agree with physiological needs in choosing their facial cream because they believe that facial cream will take care of, maintain and restore the health of the skin on the face better was rated 4.46 out of 5. However, their opinion towards on the physiological needs, or the desire of person who wants to achieve the ultimate goal, which is to use a facial cream because they want to have perfect skin was also predominantly positive as the mean score was 4.41 out of 5. Other two hierarchical needs that showed a comparable result was self-esteem needs, they believed facial cream would enhance their personality and confidence, including making friends or people around their appreciate, accepted in their complexion and radiance on their face was rated with a mean score of 3.96 but are merely driven by more safety needs because they believe that facial cream will protect their face from UV light, pollution and dust was rated with a mean score of 4.10. Finally, belongingness and love needs has still very effective on the selection of facial cream of Thai teenagers because they believed that facial cream would help restore their facial skin to be beautiful face that attracted people close to their interest and affection in their. In sum, the major from of hierarchical of needs that the Thai teenagers respondents predominantly agreed with is physiological needs, followed by self-actualization needs, safety needs, self-esteem needs and belongingness and love needs, respectively.

Level	Mean
Physiological needs	4.46
Safety needs	4.10
Belongingness and Love needs	3.69
Self-Esteem needs	3.96
Self-Actualization needs	4.41

Table 1: Thai teenagers's view on the hierarchical of needs to consuming facial cream

Summary table of frequency and percentage of Thai teenagers's selection of 5 levels of hierarchical of needs to consuming facial cream

Physiological needs

Likert Scale	Frequency	Percent
strongly disagree (1)	1	1.3
disagree (2)	3	3.8
neither agree nor disagree (3)	7	8.8
agree (4)	16	20.0
strongly agree (5)	53	66.3
Total	80	100

Somewhat similar to the mean scores based on 5-Likert scale, when the respondents were asked to choose one preferred statement that best describes their actual form of physiological needs, the major type of psychometric response scale in which responders specify their level of agreement to a

statement is strongly agree (66.3%). Following this was agree (20.0%). Furthermore, neither agree nor disagree was chosen by 8.8% of the respondents. Interestingly, a small group of Thai teenagers chose disagree and strongly disagree by 3.8% and 1.3%, respectively.

Safety needs

Likert Scale	Frequency	Percent
strongly disagree (1)	1	1.3
disagree (2)	3	3.8
neither agree nor disagree (3)	16	20.0
agree (4)	27	33.8
strongly agree (5)	33	41.3
Total	80	100

The major type of psychometric response scale in which responders specify their level of agreement to a statement is strongly agree (41.3%). Following this was agree (33.8%) which was also considered relatively high. Furthermore, neither agree nor disagree was chosen by 20% of the respondents as the preferred response. Some Thai teenagers chose disagree and strongly disagree by 3.8% and 1.3%, respectively.

Belongingness and Love needs

Likert Scale	Frequency	Percent
strongly disagree (1)	4	5.0
disagree (2)	10	12.5
neither agree nor disagree (3)	20	25.0
agree (4)	19	23.8
strongly agree (5)	27	33.8
Total	80	100

The major type of psychometric response scale in which responders specify their level of agreement to a statement is strongly agree (33.8%). Following this was neither agree nor disagree (25%) and agree (23.8%) which was also considered relatively high. Furthermore, disagree was chosen by 12.5% of the respondents as the preferred response. Interestingly, a small group of Thai teenagers chose strongly disagree by 5%.

Self-Esteem needs

Likert Scale	Frequency	Percent
strongly disagree (1)	0	0
disagree (2)	0	0
neither agree nor disagree (3)	10	12.5
agree (4)	27	33.8
strongly agree (5)	43	53.8
Total	80	100

The major type of psychometric response scale in which responders specify their level of agreement to a statement is strongly agree (53.8%). Following this was agree (33.8%) which was also considered relatively high. Furthermore, neither agree nor disagree was chosen by 12.5% of the respondents as the preferred response. Interestingly, nobody chooses disagree and strongly disagree.

Self-Actualization needs

Likert Scale	Frequency	Percent
strongly disagree (1)	2	2.5
disagree (2)	10	12.5
neither agree nor disagree (3)	13	16.3
agree (4)	19	23.8
strongly agree (5)	36	45.0
Total	80	100

The major type of psychometric response scale in which responders specify their level of agreement to a statement is strongly agree (45%). Following this was agree (23.8%) which was also considered relatively high. Furthermore, neither agree nor disagree and disagree was chosen by 16.3% and 12.5%, respectively of the respondents as the preferred response. Interestingly, a small group of Thai teenagers chose strongly disagree by 2.5%.

Based on a correlational test, the emphasis rests on the relationship between five levels of hierarchical of needs. The reason behind this is the motivation for choosing facial cream among Thai teenagers will help them understand their true needs which can contribute to meaningful experiences of using facial cream. It is important to note that only those pairs that show a correlation coefficient greater than 0.5 are considered. The analysis shows a moderate correlation between belongingness and love needs and self-esteem needs ($r=0.61$). However, the relationship between physiological needs and belongingness and love needs ($r=0.45$), the relationship between physiological and self-esteem needs ($r=0.43$), the relationship between self-esteem and self-actualization needs ($r=0.39$), the relationship between belongingness and love needs and self-actualization needs ($r=0.36$) and the relationship between physiological needs and self-actualization needs ($r=0.33$). All these can be inferred that physiological needs, self-esteem needs, belongingness and love needs and self-actualization needs are low interrelated. Additionally, when safety needs is related between self-actualization needs, belongingness and love needs and self-esteem needs will cause a very low interrelated. Correlation can be tested to have $r=0.26, 0.16, 0.14$, respectively.

Table 3: A correlational test of the 5 levels of hierarchical of needs

	Physiological	Safety	Belongness and Love	Self-Esteem	Self-Actualization
Physiological	1.00				
Safety	0.31	1.00			
Belongness and Love	0.45	0.16	1.00		
Self-Esteem	0.43	0.14	0.61	1.00	
Self-Actualization	0.33	0.26	0.36	0.39	1.00

IV. DISCUSSION

various forms of hierarchical of needs can exist when considered ranging from, basic needs to self-actualization needs. Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory points out that there could potentially be at least 5 levels of hierarchical of needs triggering one to make a critical decision. Many Thai teenagers choose to use facial cream for different reasons. If

considering at the physiological needs of using facial cream in Thai teenagers, it is found that the main reason is the general condition on our facial skin. Each other will have different facial skin care treatments. Most people choose to use facial cream because they aren't satisfied with their faces, and feel like they want to improve to better their facial skin. Therefore, it is necessary to find a way to help this level of needs come true, that makes it happen to choose to use of facial cream. Second, many Thai teenagers may choose to use facial cream because safety needs, which is not uncommon because Thailand is a country with a very hot climate. There are quite high pollution problems, such as smoke from automobile exhaust pipes, burning garbage and from industrial factory, including various dust problems caused by the construction of buildings, houses and from PM2.5. These problems are considered to be the main cause of damage to our facial skin to cause dark spots, wrinkles, acne breakouts and easily irritated. If considering the properties of facial cream in the general market, most will help maintain and restore our skin to be as good as before. Contain herbal ingredients or extracts that can help solve these problems. However, Thai teenagers are the age that needs love, belongingness, desire to be loved by others and want to have a relationship with others or be part of a group. If considering the society in the school, most students tend to group with like-minded people. It may be in the matter of education, sports, financial status or looks is another important reason that drives students to choose to be friends in school. If someone has unattractive skin, may not be accepted as part of the group of friends. They were also bullied by a group of students with bad habits. Therefore, belongingness and love needs that affects the selection of facial cream in teenagers very much. Meanwhile self-esteem needs also drives Thai teenagers to choose facial cream. As well as is generally known, teenagers are the age who want to seek uniqueness, distinctiveness and to gain recognition or admiration from those around you for yourself. Therefore, a helper in enhancing the personality give them the courage to show their faces in public or to the general public is to provide facial cream to help restore, care and call beauty, confidence to return. And the ultimate need is self-actualization needs that Maslow describes in his theory of needs. If considering the goal of Thai teenagers choosing facial cream ranging from, the basic need to this level, it will be found that they have a desire to have perfect skin, which is reasonable because the use of facial cream it takes time to show the results that our want. If using only one jar of facial cream may not be enough to the needs, which quality products it will have a relatively high price. Therefore, in order to be worth the money spent, whoever wants to get results from using the best facial cream. Finally, in the context of all needs they are all related. Human beings are living beings that have always and never ending needs, more and more. What things a human needs depends on what they gets or already have, when once a needs it has been response and the need continues. This was observed in the correlation test of the 5 levels of hierarchical of needs with all positive results and there were only very low to moderate correlations. This shows the relationship between Thai

teenagers' preferences in choosing facial cream that range from basic needs to self-actualization needs to reach their true potential.

V. CONCLUSION

This quantitative study explores the differences level of need that drive Thai teenagers to choose facial cream. Based on responses from 80 Thai teenagers aged 10-19 years, the major level of need that affects to choose to use of facial cream is physiological needs, followed by self-actualization needs. Both of these needs are considered useful in choosing facial cream among Thai teenagers. In addition, this study also pointed out the relationship between the 5 levels of needs that range from basic needs to the highest level of need to be understood and truly reach their potential. Therefore, it is worth exploring and understanding your own needs thoroughly, analyze your own facial skin problems to find and correct it or may seek advice from a dermatologist to treat and restore properly.

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